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On the Quality of Vermicompost and Millipede Compost

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ABSTRACT

Saprophagous fauna (e.g., earthworms and millipedes) involves the mineralization of plant detritus and enriches soil fertility. The quality of composts (physicochemical features and mineral composition) produced by earthworms (*Eudrilus eugeniae*) and millipedes (*Arthrosphaera magna*) in mesocosms using leaf litter with cow dung slurry has been compared in this study. Except for moisture and water-holding capacity, the rest of the features (conductivity, bulk density, specific gravity, and porosity) were significantly higher in vermicompost ($p < 0.05$) than in millipede compost. Among the nutrients, organic matter, organic carbon, nitrogen, potassium, calcium, and iron contents were significantly higher in vermicompost ($p < 0.05$) compared to millipede compost. There was no significant difference in total carbon, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, manganese, and zinc ($p > 0.05$), while chloride was below the detectable limit. Copper, selenium, silicon, aluminum, chromium, and sulfur were in trace amounts in vermicompost, while below detectable limits in millipede compost. The conversion efficiency of lignocellulosic material by saprophagous fauna may be dependent on the microbial consortium in their gut and lignocellulose. Although some amendments are necessary to improve the quality of manure, mixing suitable proportions of vermicompost and millipede compost may circumvent such inadequacy.

Keywords: Earthworms, Manure production, Nutrient evaluation, Organic matter, Saprophagous fauna

1. INTRODUCTION

Functional features of the soil ecosystem are mainly dependent on the mineralization of organic matter and elemental cycling through the saprophytic pathway by the soil biota (bacteria, fungi, and saprophagous fauna) [1, 2]. Among the global production of a large quantity of lignocellulosic organic residues, only about 14% is exploited for beneficial purposes. To enhance the soil quality and organic matter, composts produced by soil fauna are an economically viable and eco-friendly approach to agricultural production. Agricultural residues are also exploited in different ways to produce mushrooms, energy, compost, and vermicompost. There are several advantages to processing solid wastes into biobased products besides biofertilizers (e.g., biogas, bioenzymes, organic acids, bioplastics, and animal feed) [3].

The composting of organic matter and its amendment to the soil will result in improved crop growth through enhanced water and mineral absorption.

Production of vermicompost and its application is one of the most popular approaches to improving soil quality, which in turn improves agricultural productivity. Besides, vermicomposting is also an eco-friendly and viable approach to managing organic wastes produced in rural as well as urban regions [4]. Degradation of organic matter in oxygenated conditions results in the production of good soil conditioners, which cater to the needs of agriculture, gardens, and horticulture [5, 6]. Vermicompost is an aerobic process of degradation of organic matter to transform into humus by various earthworm populations within three months, which needs typical tropical environmental conditions without major investments [7-10].

Similar to vermicompost, millipede compost is also another sustainable step owing to the capability of millipedes to convert large quantities of organic matter into compost in short durations [11-15]. Large-bodied pill-millipedes of the genus *Arthrosphaera* are endemic to southern India and involved in the conversion of organic matter into humus during the monsoon season in forests and plantations [16-18]. Pill-millipedes are also known to enrich the soil's qualities through their gut microbial communities [12]. Owing to plant growth promotion, pill-millipede manure could be an effective alternative in agricultural production [11]. The current study focuses on the production and evaluation of the physicochemical and nutrient composition of composts produced by earthworms and pill-millipedes in mesocosms.

2. METHODS

2.1. Manure production

Vermicompost units of lignocellulosic waste in Yenepoya (deemed to be) University Campus facilities were used for production and assessment to compare the vermicompost and millipede compost. In three replicate units of bin (60 × 30 cm), a bed of partially decomposed native leaf litter (1 kg) was layered through mixing with cow dung slurry (10:1 w/w). The bins with organic matter were allowed to undergo primary decomposition for up to four weeks by mixing twice a week, followed by sprinkling water. Adult earthworms (*Eudrilus eugeniae*) (200 g fresh weight) were introduced into the bin for secondary decomposition for up to 42 days (Figure 1). The vermicompost was harvested after sieving to remove earthworms along with juveniles; moisture content was determined gravimetrically [19], air-dried, and stored for analysis.

Fig. 1(a-d). (a and b) Adult earthworms (*Eudrilus eugeniae*) used for vermicompost; (c) juveniles of *Eudrilus eugeniae* found after 42 days of vermicompost; (d) heap of vermicompost after 42 days.

Pill-millipedes (*Arthrosphaera magna*) occurring in plantations in the coastal region were acclimatized using moist, decaying coconut shreds for up to one month. The adult pill-millipedes (200 g fresh weight) were allowed to decompose the lignocellulosic wastes as detailed for earthworms (Figure 2). The millipede compost was harvested by sieving to remove the millipedes along with juveniles; moisture content was determined gravimetrically [19], air-dried, and stored for analysis (Figure 2).

Fig. 2(a-d). (a and b) Adult pill-millipedes (*Arthrosphaera magna*) used for millipede compost; (c) juveniles of *Arthrosphaera magna* found after 42 days of millipede compost; (d) heap of millipede compost after 42 days.

2. 2. Physical parameters

The physical properties of air-dried composts were assessed (pH, conductivity, bulk density, specific gravity, porosity, and water-holding capacity). The pH and electrical conductivity were assessed using a water analyzer (#371, Systronics India Ltd., Ahmadabad, Gujarat). The bulk density was determined by compacting a known amount of compost in graduated cylinders [20]. The specific gravity was determined following the method described in AOAC [19]. The porosity of compost was assessed based on particle density, and the water absorption capacity was determined following the procedure described by Beuchat [21].

2. 3. Nutrient analysis

Organic matter in composts was determined by the titrimetric method [22]. Organic carbon (Walkley and Black’s titration), total nitrogen (micro-Kjeldahl), and phosphorus (ascorbic acid) were evaluated based on Jackson [23]. The rest of the minerals in moisture-free composts were assessed by the field-emission scanning electron microscope-energy dispersive spectrometer analysis (SEM-EDS) (FESEM Carl Zeiss, Oxford Instruments, USA) at 15 kV [24]. The SEM images as well as the corresponding EDS spectrum of samples depend on the specific properties, such as shape, shell, and size, to calculate the mineral contents. The C/N ratio of composts was calculated based on total carbon and nitrogen.

2. 4. Statistical analysis

The variations in physical features and minerals among earthworm and millipede composts were evaluated by a *t*-test using Statistica version 8 [25].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Physical features

Moisture content ($p < 0.001$) as well as water-holding capacity ($p < 0.05$) were significantly higher in millipede compost than in vermicompost (Table 1). The pH did not significantly vary between the composts ($p > 0.05$). Conductivity ($p < 0.001$), bulk density (< 0.01), specific gravity ($p < 0.01$) and porosity ($p < 0.01$) were significantly higher in vermicompost compared to millipede compost.

Table 1. Physical features of vermicompost and millipede compost (n=3, mean \pm SD; *t*-test: *, $p < 0.05$, **, $p < 0.01$, ***, $p < 0.001$).

	Vermicompost	Millipede compost
Moisture (%)	52.93 \pm 1.05	74.66 \pm 0.59***
pH	7.25 \pm 0.07	7.67 \pm 0.25
Conductivity (μ S/cm)	256.90 \pm 6.48***	145.94 \pm 8.45
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	0.52 \pm 0.01**	0.42 \pm 0.01
Specific gravity (g/cm ³)	1.07 \pm 0.04**	0.68 \pm 0.01
Porosity (%)	57.76 \pm 2.72**	38.67 \pm 1.20
Water-holding capacity (%)	45.91 \pm 1.44	52.02 \pm 3.40*

Composts with a moisture content greater than 60% will be rigid to spread, while those with less than 40% moisture will become dusty [26]. Vermicompost in our study has 53%

moisture, which is ideal for spreading, whereas millipede compost has 75% moisture, which needs to be dried to attain below 60% moisture for easy handling. The required pH for plant growth promotion should be between 6 and 7, and both composts in our study possess a pH above the maximum range (7.3–7.7). However, the pH of both composts is consistent with the results of earlier studies [14, 27, 28]. The conductivity of composts in our study was similar to that of vermicompost and millipede composts obtained by Ramanathan and Alagesan [28].

The bulk density is the mass of compost in a unit volume, which is dependent on moisture, particle size, and compaction. The specific gravity was higher in vermicompost compared to millipede compost. The specific gravity of composts in our study is lower compared to composts produced by Thakur *et al.* [27]. Similarly, the porosity of both composts is lower than composts obtained by Thakur *et al.* [27]. The water-holding capacity of vermicompost was lower, while the millipede compost was higher compared to that obtained by Thakur *et al.* [27] and Antunes *et al.* [14]. Thus, the physical features of the composts produced in our study add value to the conversion of lignocellulosic organic matter suitable for agricultural production.

3. 2. Nutrient composition

Among the nutrients, organic matter ($p<0.01$), organic carbon ($p<0.01$), nitrogen ($p<0.001$), potassium ($p<0.01$), calcium ($p<0.05$) and iron ($p<0.01$) were significantly higher in vermicompost than in millipede compost (Table 2). Total carbon, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, manganese, copper, zinc, and chromium were not significantly different between the composts (>0.05). Chloride content was below detectable levels in both composts, whereas copper, selenium, silicon, aluminum, and sulfur were below detectable levels in millipede compost.

Table 2. Comparison of nutrients in vermicompost and millipede compost on a dry mass basis (n=3, mean \pm SD; BDL, below detectable limit; *t*-test: *, $p<0.05$, **, $p<0.01$, ***, $p<0.001$; #, Sullivan et al. 2018).

	Vermicompost	Millipede compost	Standard range [#]
Organic matter (%)	25.43 \pm 0.91**	8.36 \pm 0.56	
Organic carbon (%)	14.75 \pm 0.47**	4.89 \pm 0.32	
Total carbon (%)	32.07 \pm 0.88	31.38 \pm 1.09	
Nitrogen (%)	5.77 \pm 0.09***	4.05 \pm 0.16	1-2
Phosphorus (%)	2.52 \pm 0.30	0.14 \pm 0.02	0.3-0.9
Potassium (%)	1.26 \pm 0.11**	0.65 \pm 0.01	0.5-1.5
Calcium (%)	0.74 \pm 0.10*	0.38 \pm 0.03	1.5-3.5
Magnesium (%)	0.39 \pm 0.07	0.45 \pm 0.03	0.25-0.7
Sodium (%)	0.13 \pm 0.04	0.06 \pm 0.01	<0.6

Manganese (%)	0.03±0.01	0.03±0.01	
Iron (%)	0.47±0.06**	0.08±0.01	
Copper (%)	0.01±0.002	BDL	
Zinc (%)	0.02±0.01	0.01±0.005	
Selenium (%)	0.04±0.001	BDL	
Silicon (%)	0.04±0.01	BDL	
Chloride (%)	BDL	BDL	
Aluminum (%)	0.06±0.004	BDL	
Chromium (%)	0.02±0.005	0.01±0.006	
Sulfur (%)	0.04±0.006	BDL	0.25-0.8
C:N ratio	5.56	7.78	

Usually, organic matter will be double the organic carbon in the composts; this ratio in earthworm as well as millipede composts in our study was achieved. The carbon content of millipede compost in our study corroborates with an earlier study by Thakur *et al.* [27], which was higher than the study by Ramanathan and Alagesan [28] and lower than the compost produced by Antunes *et al.* [14]. Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, and sulfur are the important macronutrients essential for plant production [29]. If the nitrogen content in compost is more than 2%, it is considered good fertilizer and needs no additional nitrogen input [26]. In our study, both composts have a nitrogen content between 4.1% and 5.8%, indicating their adequacy. The nitrogen and phosphorus contents of millipede compost in our study are higher than those of the composts produced by Antunes *et al.* [14, 28].

Phosphorus input to agricultural fields originates mainly from organic enrichment. Phosphorus content in our study was higher in vermicompost than millipede compost. Its availability to crops is dependent on soil qualities like soil reaction, soil sorption, rainfall, calcium, aluminum, and iron contents [29-31]. Up to 80–90% of inorganic phosphorus is not available to crops owing to unfavorable soil conditions, thus requiring the input of phosphorus through composts and organic fertilizers [31]. Owing to its acidic pH (pH 6), phosphorus is bioavailable and will not be tied up with minerals like aluminum and iron. Vermicompost in our study possesses 2.5% phosphorus; hence, a supplement of phosphorus is not a requisite for agricultural applications [26]. As the millipede compost has a low phosphorus content (0.14%), it needs supplementation.

The potassium content in composts in our study was close to the desired level (0.7–1.3% vs. 0.5–1.5%), and demanded no supplementation [26]. The potassium content in both composts is higher than in the study by Ramanathan and Alagesan [28]. The sodium content (0-0.04%) is below the desired limit (<0.6%), hence it will not injure the plants [26]. As the calcium content (0.4–0.7%) was below the desired limit (1.5–3.5%), supplementation is needed

[26]. Calcium and magnesium contents in millipede compost in our study corroborate with the millipede compost produced by Antunes *et al.* [14]. However, its content in both composts was lower than the composts obtained by Ramanathan and Alagesan [28]. Magnesium content in composts is adequate according to the standard range [26]. The sodium level (0.06–0.13%) also does not exceed the desired limit (0.6%) but demands additional supply.

The C/N ratio was higher in millipede compost than in vermicompost. However, this ratio of both composts (5.6 and 7.8) was less than 10:1; hence, available nitrogen will be immediately accessible to crops receiving these composts for a short duration [26]. The C:N ratio of composts in our study was lower than the studies carried out by Antunes *et al.* [14] and Ramanathan and Alagesan [28]. Some reports demonstrated improvements in plant production using vermicompost and millipede compost [14, 28, 32]. Selecting appropriate organic matter to produce compost is a very important strategy. Utilization of fallen leaf litter amended with cow dung slurry in the present study is an appropriate feedstock to enhance the compost quality.

As in the present study, vermicomposting needs a duration of 45–60 days [4], while millipede compost could be produced within 30 days, which is advantageous for the quick turnover of lignocellulosic wastes. According to Rajkumar *et al.* [33], millipede compost yield is higher than vermicompost on kitchen wastes in Tamil Nadu, southern India, which supports our study.

Millipede compost production is a fairly new alternative technique to vermicompost, and it was also used for the sustainable cultivation of broccoli in Brazil [14]. Similarly, millipede composts are useful in raising the forest nurseries in Tamil Nadu [34]. Millipede compost is also known to support many beneficial microbes, including growth-enhancing rhizobia, as a value addition in organic agriculture [11].

4. CONCLUSIONS

Utilization of surplus lignocellulosic wastes is one of the feasible endeavors towards self-sufficiency in organic agriculture. The current study focused on compost production using decomposing leaf litter with cow dung slurry by earthworms and millipedes in mesocosms. The rate of bioconversion efficiency was higher in millipedes compared to earthworms, which may depend on the gut microbial consortia of saprophytic fauna and the microbiota of feedstock.

The physical features and nutrient composition of the composts produced in our study are a valuable addition, although some constituents need amendment. It may be possible to achieve the desired physicochemical and nutritional properties by the appropriate mixing of vermicompost and millipede compost. In addition to leaf litter and cow dung, amendment of certain quantities of soil will also be useful in improving the qualities of manure. Decomposing leaf litter, vegetable waste, cow dung slurry, and soil constitute good feedstock for the production of value-added manures using earthworms and millipedes.

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